

Seemee – Solar Solutions

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INTRODUCTION

Seemee provides a solution to the problem of advertising on bikes in low light conditions. The Seemee system provides a controllable light source powered by renewable energy through solar cells which advertisers can use to improve advert visibility at night time. The system can also power front- and backlights and thereby target the private bike market.

THEORY

The system utilize solar cells to charge a rechargeable battery through the day, whereby at night the system will be charged and ready to light up commercials and cyclist with low powered LED's

RESULTS

The electronics is still under development, but the lit commercial plate has been installed on a bike to test visibility at nighttime. The system appears well integrated into the bike and gives a good clear view of the commercial even in very low light conditions.

CONCLUSION

As it is not presently possible for the citybike bike schemes to light up their ads as this would demand too much maintenance and time changing batteries, there is a market for the product. As the group has been in contact with different bike scheme providers we are fairly confident that there is an interest in our product.

Furthermore the product could be a good alternative for the private customers who want a system that is installed and then demands no further work to function.